

Performance of CFS floor-to-wall subassemblies under accidental loss of support

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ABSTRACT

Offsite modern methods of construction, such as cold-formed steel (CFS) panelised construction, provide short- and long-term solutions to some of the most critical issues associated with traditional construction such as high carbon emissions, long construction periods, construction labour shortages, and high costs. However, current structural design guidance is lacking for CFS panelised construction, particularly for disproportionate collapse loading scenarios such as accidental loss of support. Designers often rely on inappropriate tie force requirements in the design of CFS structures. When subject to loss of support, CFS structures may experience large beam deflections and significant rotations and tension in the connections, the combination of which has not been investigated. This paper presents results from a full-scale test on floor joists-to-wall stud subassemblies to evaluate their connection behaviour under support removal. This paper evaluates the performance of a typical industry connection and its robustness against disproportionate collapse under accidental support removal in CFS panelised structures.

Keywords: Cold-formed steel, disproportionate collapse, screwed connections, support removal

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 General

The availability and affordability of adequate residential dwellings presents an economic and social concern in the EU as well as worldwide (1) (2) (3). For the past decades, countries have consistently missed house-building targets, leading to an increase in prices, which result in homelessness and housing cost overburden (4). Such deficit in housing supply-to-demand, if not addressed, is only expected to exacerbate due to population growth, ageing of societies, migration, increasing urbanisation, land scarcity and construction labour shortages (as reported by 20% of EU companies) (5). Moreover, embodied carbon from the construction industry, i.e. associated with materials and construction processes throughout a building's lifecycle, contributes to 11% of global carbon emissions (as of December 2017) (6). Around 40% of Europe's solid urban waste is construction and demolition waste, 54% of which ends up in landfills (7). To achieve residential building demands, which cannot be met using traditional construction methods, and UN sustainable development goals, particularly, sustainable cities and communities (Goal 11) and climate action (Goal 13), there is a pressing need for more responsible construction policies (1).

Fig. 1. Percentage of residential buildings constructed with MMC in different countries worldwide (10)

Offsite modern methods of construction (MMC) have been lauded for their ability to meet building targets while achieving high quality and sustainability credentials (8). Cold formed steel (CFS) load-bearing wall (or panelised) construction, is an increasingly popular MMC that offers remarkable advantages to its hot-rolled steel (HRS) counterparts including higher strength-to-weight ratio, high durability, lighter weight, and thus, ease of handling, shorter build times, and reduced construction-related carbon emissions (e.g. foundation requirements) (9). Despite the benefits of MMC, uptake has been low (see Fig. 1) (10), largely due to lack of: guidelines, reliable connection systems, training, and capital investment.

CFS panels are the basic load bearing members currently used in this type of steel construction (11). Their use covers a wide range of structural systems in residential, commercial, and industrial buildings. Connections of these types of buildings are usually made by screws or rivets, which can be categorized as semi-rigid connections (12). In practice, building members are designed to meet normal and accidental loading conditions (13). An accidental loading situation may occur due to the impact of a vehicle, a gas explosion, or a terrorist attack (14). Such accidental loading scenarios can result in localised structural failure, which if transmitted to other parts of the structure, can cause a chain reaction resulting in the collapse of the entire structure in what is known as progressive collapse. The fulfilment of limit states in under normal loading conditions may not be sufficient in such accidental conditions due to the loss of support (13).

CFS structures are often designed using existing codes or standards, at component level, but do not take into consideration how the real interactions between components in CFS panelised construction affect their performance. This can lead to inefficient and/or unsafe designs. The key to unlocking design efficiency is to firstly understand existing typical connection performance behaviour. This will be the first step to truly understanding the load redistribution and collapse mechanisms, particularly under disproportionate collapse load scenarios.

1.2 Research Significance

There are very few analytical studies regarding the progressive collapse performance of CFS panelised structures (15), while no experimental studies could be found. This has been attributed to the fact that CFS structures have been assumed “not to be susceptible to that kind of failure or collapse owing to their inherent structural redundancy” (15). However, with the increased use of offsite construction methods using CFS panelised components, particularly in mid-rise structural systems, the possibility of progressive collapse of CFS structures has become a critical issue. This study will serve as a first attempt to address this research need. Fig. 2 shows the first two storeys in a CFS 2D panelised structure with notional element removal, i.e. where internal wall panels have been removed. The structural performance of the out-of-plane supporting structure directly above

the removed panels consists of in-plane track sections and out-of-plane joists are considered in this present study. Details of the performed test are discussed in the subsequent sections.

Fig. 2. Elevation view of bottom two storeys in a panelised structure with notional element (panels) removal. The structure immediately above the removed panels are the track sections (in-plane) and floor joists (out-of-plane) are considered in the testing

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

2.1 Test Set-up

Fig. 3 presents the test set-up for the track and joist tests, referred to as the floor-to-wall (F-W) subassemblies, under the scenario of notional panel support removal. These tests were undertaken in the Structural Laboratory in the School of Civil Engineering at University College Dublin (UCD). The central stud was loaded by a monotonic static push-down load from a hydraulic actuator, as shown in Fig. 3. The central stud was guided at the bottom within a sliding support which allows a maximum vertical free movement of about 250 mm. The test was terminated when the specimen failed globally.

Fig. 3. Experimental test set-up of floor to wall (F-W) test subassembly

2.2 Instrumentation

Displacement transducers (LVDTs) were arranged to measure the vertical deflection of the F-W subassembly and to determine the connection rotation angle as shown in Fig. 4. As such, LVDTs were located at both stud flanges (L3 and L4), at the bottom flanges of the two joists at midspan (L2 and L5) and near the joists ends to monitor any displacements near the two pin supports, as demonstrated in Fig. 4 (L1 and L6). Measured results showed there were very little movements at the pin supports, indicating the effective restraints at the beam ends. Strain gauges were located at different locations along the joist sections as shown in Fig. 4 (e.g. 1A, 2A, etc).

Fig. 4. Schematic elevation view of left and right joist and track connection at centre. Schematic indicates LVDT and strain gauge instrumentation locations

2.3 Test Specimens

Specimens are chosen based on connections used in practical construction practice. Test specimens were supplied by a private construction practitioner that designs, manufactures and supplies CFS panelised construction solutions. Specimens were fabricated using Z-sections, lipped C-sections and U-sections. Connection detailing of the tested specimen is shown in Fig. 5 (a). Fig. 5 (b) shows the 3D isometric view of the F-W junction assembly. All sections had a nominal thickness of 1.5mm and were rolled from S450GD+Z hot-dipped galvanised steel coil with Z275 Zinc coating as per EN 10346:2015. The dimensions of the individual components are as detailed in Table 1. Figs. 5 (c and d) shows the individual component in exploded 2D and 3D view of the F-W assembly respectively.

Self-drilling tek screws (5.5 x 25mm) were used to connect all elements, apart from the stud-to-track elements (Lipped C-section-1), which were connected using self-piercing rivets, as per standard practice. The specimen was assembled as follows; to form the horizontal elements, the joists (horizontal, lipped C-section-2) were connected to the rims (horizontal, U-section), orientated at 90 degrees to the plane of the joist, using two screws top and bottom. To form the vertical elements, stud to track connections (lipped C-section-1) were connected using rivets. To assemble the full vertical component of the specimen, two Z sections were hung off either end of the track of the bottom vertical element (consisting of a stud and track) and each Z section was screwed into the stud flange through its web using two tek screws. The top stud and track vertical component was then placed on top of the Z section and aligned with the bottom vertical element and connected using two screws that go through two tracks and the Z section. To form the joint between horizontal and vertical elements, four screws were used to connect each horizontal element (through the joist rim or U-section) to the vertical members (through the Z-section). These screws were centred on the Z-section 80mm vertically and 140mm apart horizontally. Finally, two screws were used to connect the bottom flange to the Z hanger and the bottom flange of the joists.

Table 1. Dimension of the specimen components

Serial No.	Component	Dimension (in mm)	Thickness (in mm)
1	Lipped C-section-1	90 × 50 × 13	1.5
2	Lipped C-section-2	200 × 50 × 13	1.5
3	Z Section	200 × 100 × 40	1.5
4	U-section	200 × 50	1.5

Fig.5. Details of the tested specimen; a) connection details; b) 3D Isometric view; c and d) exploded 2D and 3D views respectively showing individual components.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The subsequent sections present results from a single F-W tested specimen. This research is part of an ongoing experimental and numerical study examining the performance of different CFS joints' performances when subjected to a loss of support scenario. Test details of the tested F-W specimen are discussed in the subsequent sections.

3.1 Failure Modes

The test specimen failed in the connection region. The progression of failure observed at the connection region is shown in Figs. 6a, b, c, and d, which show the deformation of the at the centre of the F-W assembly junction at 40%, 70% and 90% of the peak load respectively. Figs. 6 (a and b) show that the specimen initially experienced a pull-out failure of screws and separation of the joint (comprising the lipped C section-2 and the U-section) from the vertical stud component (joined to the joist section through the Z-section). The tested specimen exhibited severe plastic deformation (Fig. 6 (c)) followed by a global collapse as observed in Fig. 6 (d).

Fig. 6. Observed failure modes in the test specimen; a-c) connection failures and separation between CFS joist and stud at the F-W assembly at various stages of loading; d) total collapse of the specimen

3.2 Load-displacement relationship and damage evolution

The test was conducted in several parts as the stroke of the LVDTs was limited and they had to be reset when they reached their stroke limit (in particular L3 and L4 in Fig. 4). Fig. 7 shows the load (F) – displacement (δ) relationship of the mid-point of the junction of the tested subassemblies obtained in the last part of the test prior to failure which shows a displacement of up to 120 mm (the final 120mm), however in total the specimen was subjected to a maximum displacement of up to approximately 600mm. There were 7 loading phases in total due to LVDT stroke limitations. The F vs. δ curve shows the global vertical stiffness behaviour of the connection prior to failure. It can be seen that the failure is brittle, but notable stiffness remains up to final collapse. The load drop observed from points f to g was due to separation between CFS joists and stud at the F-W assembly junction as shown in Fig. 6 (c). Global collapse occurred after point h as can be seen in Fig. 6(d).

Fig. 7. Final phase of the load (F) – displacement (δ) response of the tested specimen

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Research and guidance on the robust design of CFS panelised load-bearing wall construction is still lacking. Some reasons for this are a lack of physical tests and a resulting lack of understanding the true mechanism through which load is redistributed through CFS panelised construction in notional element support removal scenarios. This paper presents experimental results from an ongoing study examining connection behaviour and load redistribution of floor joists in CFS panelised structures. Further experimental studies and validated non-linear finite element FE models are being carried out on different configurations of the F-W sub-assemblies with various sectional geometries and connection details.

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